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Time, Memory and Denial in Kazuo Ishiguro's *An Artist of the Floating World*

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Abstract:

This research paper explores how Kazuo Ishiguro's *An Artist of the Floating World* (1986) turns time as a background element unravelling a moral exploration of denial and recognition. The novel's slow pace and delayed revelations are not only stylistic choices but reflect how the narrator, Masuji Ono, avoids directly confronting his past and his sense of guilt. As Ono reflects his past actions, his uncertainty stretch across time showing how memory and guilt emerge only through recollection and gradual recognition. As a reader, I experienced this same hesitation, piecing together fragments and omissions to understand denial. This fragmented narrative technique suggests that moral understanding develops slowly through time and reflection. Drawing on Paul Ricoeur's idea that narrative shapes ethical understanding, this paper explored how Ishiguro uses time as a space where moral awareness develop gradually rather than immediately. Following Gérard Genette's narrative discourse, the novel's structure can be seen as a play of order, duration, and frequency particularly through anachrony where past and present intermingle, and through analepsis where memories are revisited after a gap creating a sense of delay and repetition that mirrors Ono's self-avoidance. Cathy Caruth's concept of trauma as belatedness further clarifies how Ono's

memories resurface slowly, suggesting that denial is a form of postponed recognition rather than simple forgetting. Finally, Axel Honneth's theory of recognition gives this temporal process ethical meaning; he further argues that moral growth and social reconciliation depend on the willingness to acknowledge self and others truthfully. Ono's slow admission of guilt reflects this struggle; his moral recovery requires not only remembering the past but also recognizing the harm done.

Keywords: Denial, recognition, guilt, moral growth, belatedness, memory, nationalism.

Introduction:

Kazuo Ishiguro's *An Artist of the Floating World* unfolds in the shadow of Japan's defeat in the Second World War, narrated by Masuji Ono, a retired artist who recalls his life with calm detachment and measured dignity. Set between 1948 and 1950, the novel depicts a society negotiating the moral and cultural ruins of imperial ideology as it reconstructs its identity under the emerging influence of American occupation. Ono's recollections trace his artistic journey from the pleasure-seeking "floating world" of traditional aesthetics to the politically charged propagandist art that supported nationalist sentiment during the war. As his narration unfolds, what appears to be a story of memory and self-reflection gradually reveals itself as a complex act of self-justification as he tries to justify his role in propaganda. Ono's reminiscences are fragmented, temporally unstable, and punctuated by omissions, hesitations, and digressions that raise profound questions about how individuals come to know – or refuse to know – their own moral complicity.

This paper uses close reading, narratological analysis, and ethical interpretation to examine how Ishiguro's manipulation of time shapes denial and recognition.

While much of the critical discourse focuses on unreliable narration, guilt, and the ethics of memory, less attention was given to 'how time structures these moral evasions'. In the novel,

temporality is not a neutral background but an active mechanism of denial. It employs intricate manipulation of narrative time – its recursive flashbacks, suspended revelations, and protracted confessions that render the act of remembering a site or moral deferral rather than discovery. This paper proposes that Ishiguro transforms the very experience of narrative temporality into an ethical structure of postponement where the passage of time becomes the psychological medium through which Ono protects his self-image from collapse.

Theoretical Framework:

This paper draws on four key theoretical perspectives to examine how time, memory, and denial interact in Ishiguro's novel. Each framework provides a different lens for interpreting the novel's shifting temporal structure and the psychological and ethical tensions that shape Ono's retrospective narrative.

In *Time and Narrative*, Paul Ricoeur argues that narrative transforms time into ethical experience, shaping how individuals understand themselves through their stories. Memory, in this view, is not a simple retrieval of facts but a reconstruction shaped by present needs and moral pressures. Ono's hesitant recollections – alternating between pride, defensiveness, and doubt – illustrate this process. His story changes as he tells it, revealing the ethical struggle involved in reinterpreting his past.

Gérard Genette's concepts of anachrony, analepsis, and duration help explain how Ishiguro structures Ono's story. Flashbacks appear late, and key moments – such as Kuroda's arrest – are withheld or shortened, producing what Genette calls temporal dislocation. These structural choices mirror Ono's reluctance to confront uncomfortable truths and create a narrative rhythm in which moral recognition was delayed.

Cathy Caruth's theory of trauma as belatedness adds a psychological dimension to this temporal instability. Trauma, Caruth argues, becomes fully visible only after a delay. Ono's

scattered, contradictory recollections of wartime events reflect this pattern: they return only when prompted, often incomplete or unclear forms. His reluctance and fragmentation suggest that guilt functions like – emerging late and unevenly.

Axel Honneth's theory of recognition provides an ethical perspective. For Honneth, moral life depends on acknowledging oneself and others truthfully. Ono's gradual admission of responsibility, though hesitant and incomplete, represents a struggle toward this form of recognition. His narrative reveals how ethical self-understanding requires time, humility, and willingness to see one's past anew.

Analysis:

Early Self-Assurance and Selective Memory:

Masuji Ono's narration in *An Artist of the Floating World* begins with an unmistakable tone of confidence. He writes as a man who believes he has lived a meaningful, accomplished life, and who assumes that his account carries natural authority. This early sense of assuredness was deeply intertwined with his selective use of memory. His memory is never purely individual; it is constantly measured against how others might see him. Maurice Halbwachs' concept of collective memory is crucial here: what can be remembered is conditioned by social frameworks. Although Ono claims to be offering a straightforward recollection of the events that shaped his career and family life, the narrative reveals that he chooses to highlight episodes that reinforce his dignity while relegating more compromising moments to the background. Ricoeur's theory suggests that this selective storytelling reflects Ono's desire to maintain a stable narrative identity.

His account of his artistic development exemplifies this tendency. Ono describes his early defiance of his father, who burned his paintings in hopes to discourage him from becoming an artist, as an act of principled determination. He frames his years in the factory-like studio

and later in Moriyama's villa as crucial steps in the making of a serious artist, suggesting that he belonged naturally among the gifted students who depicted the pleasures of the city's nightlife. Moments of conflict, such as Moriyama's disappointment upon discovering Ono's political interests, are narrated cautiously, with Ono placing emphasis on his own courage rather than on the tension he caused. The same self-selection characterizes his recollections of Matsuda, whose encouragement of political engagement Ono remembers as a kind of moral awakening rather than as a departure that damaged an important relationship.

The selective nature of Ono's memories becomes evident when he discusses the years after the war, during which he attempts to arrange a marriage for his daughter Noriko. The collapse of an earlier marriage negotiation, which he attributes vaguely to misunderstandings, is not examined in detail. Instead, he focuses on his elder daughter, Setsuko's polite advice that he should visit old acquaintances before the new negotiations proceed. Ono interprets this as a gentle suggestion that he must make his past "less of a problem," however, he glosses over the degree to which his reputation, shaped by his wartime career, genuinely threatens Noriko's prospects. In these early sections, his self-assurance masks an unwillingness to confront the full implications of his past, and his memories serve as instruments to protect the version of himself he prefers to see.

Cracks in the Story and Contradictions:

As Ono's narrative progresses, its confident surface begins to fracture, revealing inconsistencies and subtle contradictions. Ishiguro structures the novel so that Ono's recollections shift in emphasis each time he revisits them, gradually exposing the tensions between what he claims and what the unfolding context suggests. These contradictions do not present Ono as deceptive in a deliberate sense; instead, they reveal a man compelled by emotional need to reinterpret his past. Genette's notion of analepsis explains how delayed revelations force reinterpretation.

One of the most telling examples involves his relationship with Kuroda, once his favored pupil. Ono initially speaks of Kuroda with a sense of paternal pride, though he notes the student's "unpatriotic tendencies" with an air of mild disapproval. It is only gradually, through layers of narrative revision, that he acknowledges his role in reporting Kuroda to the wartime authorities. Even then, the severity of his actions emerges slowly. The memory of watching police officers burn Kuroda's paintings—an image that echoes the burning of his own work by his father—is at first described with detachment, only later taking on emotional weight when it becomes clear that this betrayal permanently severed the relationship.

Similar contradictions arise in his portrayal of Moriyama. Ono's early depiction of his break from the studio emphasizes independence and artistic evolution. Nevertheless, as he revisits the memory, the tone shifts, and the episode appears increasingly fraught with disappointment and wounded pride. The more Ono recalls, the more apparent it becomes that he has been smoothing the edges of a painful rupture.

These narrative fissures parallel the discomfort Ono experiences in the post-war setting. His irritation with the younger, Americanized generation—whom he believes resent his own generation for leading the nation into disaster—sits uneasily alongside his insistence that his wartime work was respected and even admired. The more he encounters people who quietly distance themselves from his past, the more his narrative strains to maintain coherence. It is through these contradictions that Ishiguro allows Ono's defenses to slip, revealing a deeper internal struggle beneath the polished surface of the story he tries to tell.

Wartime Responsibility and Deferred Guilt:

Ono's recollections of the war years form the troubled core of his narrative, and they reveal a complex relationship of guilt and responsibility. Although he once rose to prominence producing nationalistic art that celebrated the "new spirit" of Japan and even gained influence as part of a committee that censored politically undesirable works, he rarely confronts the full

implications of these activities. His sense of responsibility emerges hesitantly, which is explained as the fragmented return of guilt by Caruth, filtered through years of self-justification and the abrupt shift in public values that followed Japan's defeat.

The novel shows that Ono's wartime career was not simply a matter of artistic direction but one of significant political engagement. His participation in censorship, especially his denunciation of Kuroda, had severe and lasting consequences. However, Ono recounts these actions in a tone oscillating between pride and regret. He acknowledges that he acted decisively and with conviction, but he is also haunted by the possibility that his decisions contributed to a destructive national ideology and to personal tragedies. His bitterness toward the post-war generation suggests an unspoken defensiveness, as though their changing attitudes threaten the foundations of his identity.

This deferred guilt is intensified by the personal losses he suffered during the war. Genette's concept of duration asserts how Ishiguro devotes little narrative time to the most painful moments, reinforcing their emotional difficulty. The deaths of his wife Michiko and his son Kenji weigh heavily on him, even though he rarely articulates the connection between their deaths and the ideology he supported. Instead, his guilt surfaces indirectly through moments of melancholy, through his fixation on Noriko's failed marriage negotiation, and through his increasing awareness that his reputation has become an obstacle rather than an asset.

Ono's narrative neither absolves nor condemns him outright. Instead, it shows a man who is gradually forced to recognize the discrepancy between the self-image he once cherished and the darker realities of the past. His guilt is never fully confronted; it surfaces in fragments and retreats again into the protective folds of memory. The war did not only alter the nation's course; it left Ono with a burden of responsibility he can acknowledge only slowly and incompletely.

Recognition and Acceptance:

By the end of the novel, Ono moves toward a quiet, modest form of acceptance, though it remains partial and uncertain. This shift begins with his interactions with his family, especially Setsuko, who in her understated way encourages him to consider how his past might be perceived by others. Her suggestion that he meet with old acquaintances before Noriko's marriage negotiations, though politely phrased, forces Ono to acknowledge that the world may not view his past as favorably as he does. This realization introduces a current of shame that subtly alters the tone of his narration.

Recognition comes most clearly through his encounter with Kuroda, whose refusal to see him during the negotiations conveys a judgment far more powerful than explicit accusation. Ono is compelled to confront the real consequences of his wartime decisions when Kuroda's lingering resentment cannot be softened by his attempts at courteous explanation. This moment stands as the emotional pivot of the novel, where Ono no longer has access to the soothing narratives he once used to frame his actions. This dynamic resonates with Axel Honneth's argument that ethical life depends upon reciprocal acknowledgment, and that the failure to recognize or to be recognized by others produces a profound form of moral injury.

His conversation with Setsuko after Noriko's successful marriage hints at the beginning of acceptance. When she tells him that his paintings were admired but ultimately not influential enough to have caused serious harm, Ono is confronted with the unsettling idea that his reputation may be more negligible than dangerous. He must reconcile genuine guilt for his betrayals with the realization that he may not have been the significant cultural figure he once considered himself to be. This ambivalence between remorse and diminished pride marks his internal shifting.

The final chapters show him adopting a quieter, more reflective attitude. Matsuda's death, which he receives calmly, signals the end of a shared ideological past, and he chooses not to

revisit their debates or their ambitions. Instead, he finds small pleasures in observing younger businessmen who, to his surprise, display echoes of the "floating world" he once depicted. Most importantly, he turns his attention to his grandson Ichiro, whose innocence and enthusiasm offer him a sense of continuity that neither his career nor his past convictions can provide.

Ono's acceptance is not a grand moral revelation but a modest adjustment of self-understanding. It suggests a man who has begun to loosen his grip on old certainties, who acknowledges his errors without entirely redefining himself through them. Ishiguro offers no dramatic confession, only the quiet recognition that life continues, and that meaning might be found not in one's past stature but in small, present acts of connection.

Conclusion:

Kazuo Ishiguro's *An Artist of the Floating World* presents time as the central medium through which denial and moral awareness unfold. It reveals that memory is not simply a storehouse of the past but a fluid, interpretive act that is constantly revised in response to present anxieties. Ono's narrative moves from self-assurance to uncertainty, revealing how memory is shaped by what self can bear. His recollections are shaped by trauma, though his trauma is not the traditional one of victimhood; rather it is the trauma of complicity, of being part of a failed imperialist nationalist. His denial is not merely a personal flaw, but it is a manifestation of a broader cultural struggle in post-war Japan, where the remnants of imperial ideology collide with the demands of a democratic modernity. Ricoeur explains how narrative time structures self-understanding; Genette shows how the novel's delays and omissions reflect Ono's avoidance; Caruth clarifies why guilt returns late and incompletely; and Honneth highlights the ethical importance of recognition.

The novel suggests that confronting the past requires time, hesitation, and gradual acknowledgment. Denial is not simply forgetting but a complex temporal strategy for managing guilt. The setting of 1948-1950 Japan intensifies Ono's temporal disorientation. As John Dower observes in *Embracing Defeat*, post-war Japan underwent an upheaval in values, institutions, and social hierarchies. Those who had aligned themselves with pre-war nationalism found their previous convictions discredited. In such a context, the past was not merely a personal memory; it was a national burden. Ishiguro demonstrates that moral knowledge does not arrive through sudden confession but through the long, uneasy process of remembering and reinterpreting one's actions. What Paul Ricoeur describes as ethical hermeneutics suggests that understanding arises not from immediacy of truth but from the temporal labor of interpretation. Reader's gradual realization mirrors Ono's delayed recognition. Unlike the narrator, the reader is aware of this deferral as it happens. Ishiguro thus transforms reading itself into an ethical act, which is an experience of temporal discomfort that echoes the moral unease of postwar remembrance. The reader becomes a witness to the gap between knowing and acknowledging. Though his memory was neither fully honest nor fully deceptive, it was a complex negotiation between guilt and self-preservation. In this way, the novel turns temporality into an ethical force, revealing how individuals – and perhaps nations – face their histories only slowly, through the unfolding rhythms of memory. “One can only wish these young people well.”(Ishiguro 206) This closing line perfectly encapsulates the subtle but decisive shift in Ono's relationship with memory and self-justification. Stripped of the earlier insistence on influence, authority, or moral significance, this sentence signals not a moment of confession or redemption, but a relinquishment of narrative centrality. He no longer positions himself as a figure whose past actions demand recognition or judgment instead he recedes into muted resignation of his idealized memory of self-preservation. He gradually arrives at a form of ethical quietude that

neither fully acknowledges guilt nor aggressively defends innocence. Time, in this final moment, is no longer something to be mastered through memory, but something that moves beyond him. The future belongs to those unburdened by the ideological failures of the past, while Ono's role is reduced to observation rather than intervention.

Ishiguro thus resists narrative closure rooted in moral reckoning; instead, he offers a conclusion shaped by historical displacement and emotional attrition. Ending of the novel affirms that in a post-war world structured by forgetting as much as remembrance, denial need not collapse dramatically; it may fade into silence, leaving behind a fragile, diminished self who can do little more than wish the next generation well.

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